

NEFI Project Handbook

Version 1.1

NEFI – Project handbook

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1. Change directory

Document owner: RA (AIT)

The project plan is a living document and shall continuously be adapted and expanded during the duration of the project.

Version number	Date	Changes	Creator
1.0	19.09.24	First working draft	RA, PS
1.1	13.03.25	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Update ministry designation – Update and detailing of the interface NEFI – KLIEN – BMIMI – Update team members – Title Page – List of Hub co-leads and NEFI facilitators – Acknowledgements update 	RA
1.2	19.09.25	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Update List of Hub co-leads – Update Table: Risk analysis and risk mitigation – Update Operative Team 	PS

2. NEFI team

Table 1: NEFI contact details

Initials	Name	Affiliation	Email address	Role
NEFI network steering committee				
BG	Bernhard Gahleitner	AIT	bernhard.gahleitner@ait.ac.at	Network coordinator, steering committee
TK	Thomas Kienberger	MUL	thomas.kienberger@unileoben.ac.at	NEFI+ coordinator, steering committee
DW	Dorian Wessely	BIZ UP	dorian.wessely@biz-up.at	Steering committee
CE	Christiane Egger	ESV	christiane.egger@esv.or.at	Steering committee
Operative team				
RA	Renate Auer	AIT	renate.auer@ait.ac.at	Monitoring, impact assessment
EB	Elena Balbekova	BIZ	elena.balbekova@biz-up.at	Task Lead, Operative support
MD	Marianne Doletschek	MUL	marianne.doletschek@unileoben.ac.at	Data management, Operative & strategic support
MG	Michael Grünwald	BIZ	michael.gruenwald@biz-up.at	Operative support
IH	Irmgard Herold	AIT	irmgard.herold@ait.ac.at	Marketing and communication
KHL	Karl-Heinz Leitner	AIT	karl-heinz.leitner@ait.ac.at	Task lead
SN	Stefanie Nagler	AIT	Stefanie.Nagler@ait.ac.at	Hub coordination,

				Inter-nationalisation
CÖ	Christine Öhlinger	ESV	christine.oehlinger@esv.or.at	Exploitation
MÖ	Margit Özelt	AIT	margit.oezelt@ait.ac.at,	Marketing and communication
KPS	Kerstin Pflieger-Schopf	MUL	kerstin.pfleger-schopf@unileoben.ac.at	NEFI+ operative coordination, Hub coordination
GR	Gustav Resch	AIT	gustav.resch@ait.ac.at	Task lead
OS	Oxana Schmidt	AIT	Oxana.Schmidt@ait.ac.at	Marketing and communication
CS	Christian Schützenhofer	AIT	christian.schuetzenhofer@ait.ac.at	Task lead
PS	Petra Sleziakova	MUL	petra.sleziakova@unileoben.ac.at	Milestone plan, Quality assurance.
GT	Gersa Tome	AIT	Gersa.tome@ait.ac.at	Task lead VIL
TT	Tanja Tötzer	AIT	Tanja.toetzer@ait.ac.at	Task lead
LW	Lukas Wechner	MUL	lukas.wechner@unileoben.ac.at	Transformation support, scenarios

At the center of NEFI are the **NEFI Innovation Hubs**, specialist networks that initiate critical research and innovation projects. Each Hub is led by two or three prestigious research institutions, so called **Hub Co-leads**, which are developing significant and practical research and demonstration projects in collaboration with industry partners. At the operational level, hubs receive support from NEFI, specifically through members of the NEFI operative team. The primary points of contact for the hubs are the **facilitators** as listed in the following table:

Table 2: NEFI Innovation Hubs with Hub co-leads and facilitators

	Affiliation	Expert / Facilitator	Email address
CCUS			
Hub Co lead	AIT	Gerwin Drexler-Schmid	Gerwin.drexler-schmid@ait.ac.at
	MUL	Christoph Markowitsch	christoph.markowitsch@unileoben.ac.at
	TU Graz	Marlene Kienberger	Marlene.kienberger@tugraz.at
NEFI facilitator	AIT	Renate Auer	renate.auer@ait.ac.at
		Stefanie Nagler	Stefanie.Nagler@ait.ac.at
	MUL	Susanne Hochmeister	Susanne.hochmeister@unileoben.ac.at
Circular Economy			
Hub Co lead	AEE	Bettina Muster-Slawtisch	b.muster@aee.at
	Intec		
	EI at JKU	Karin Fazeni-Fraisl	fazeni@energieinstitut-linz.at
NEFI facilitator	AIT	Oxana Schmidt	Oxana.Schmidt@ait.ac.at
		Irmgard Herold	Irmgard.herold@ait.ac.at
	BIZ UP	Elena Balbekova	elena.balbekova@biz-up.at
CO₂-neutral Gases & Hydrogen			
Hub Co lead	AIT	Stephan Abermann	Stephan.Abermann@ait.ac.at
	EI at JKU	Robert Tichler	tichler@energieinstitut-linz.at
		Andreas Zauner	zauner@energieinstitut-linz.at
	HyCentA	Fabian Radner	radner@hycenta.at
		Alexander Trattner	trattner@hycenta.at
Franz Winkler		winkler@hycenta.at	
NEFI facilitator	AIT	Oxana Schmidt	Oxana.Schmidt@ait.ac.at
		Irmgard Herold	Irmgard.herold@ait.ac.at
	BIZ UP	Elena Balbekova	elena.balbekova@biz-up.at
	ESV	Christine Öhlinger	christine.oehlinger@esv.or.at
	MUL	Lukas Wechner	lukas.wechner@unileoben.ac.at
Electrification & Energy Efficiency			
Hub Co lead	AIT	Thomas Fleckl	thomas.fleckl@ait.ac.at
		Veronika Wilk	veronika.wilk@ait.ac.at
	MUL	David Banasiak	david.banasiak@unileoben.ac.at
		Markus Makoschitz	markus.makoschitz@unileoben.ac.at
NEFI facilitator	AIT	Renate Auer	renate.auer@ait.ac.at

		Stefanie Nagler	Stefanie.Nagler@ait.ac.at
	ESV	Christine Öhlinger	christine.oehlinger@esv.or.at
Flexibility			
Hub Co lead	AIT	Tara Esterl	tara.esterl@ait.ac.at
	MUL	Kerstin Pflieger-Schopf	kerstin.pflieger-schopf@unileoben.ac.at
NEFI facilitator	AIT	Renate Auer	renate.auer@ait.ac.at
		Stefanie Nagler	Stefanie.Nagler@ait.ac.at
	ESV	Christine Öhlinger	christine.oehlinger@esv.or.at
Industrial Symbiosis			
Hub Co lead	AEE	Christoph Brunner	c.brunner@aee.at
	INTEC	Wolfgang Gruber-Glatzl	w.gruber-glatzl@aee.at
	MUL	Kerstin Pflieger-Schopf	kerstin.pflieger-schopf@unileoben.ac.at
NEFI facilitator	AIT	Oxana Schmidt	Oxana.Schmidt@ait.ac.at
		Irmgard Herold	Irmgard.herold@ait.ac.at
	BIZ UP	Elena Balbekova	elena.balbekova@biz-up.at

3. Purpose of the NEFI project handbook

The purpose of this project handbook is to serve as a comprehensive guide that (a) simplifies the **onboarding process for new team members** and (b) serves as a **reference and orientation tool** in case of uncertainties, ensuring smooth project execution. It provides a clear framework for collaboration, outlining the rules and expectations for working together effectively. The handbook also establishes well-defined communication structures, both internally (e.g. CSC, operative team, hub co-leads, project leaders) and with external stakeholders such as funding agencies.

Additionally, it lays the foundation for efficient data management and quality assurance, ensuring that all project-related information is handled with precision and care. By mapping out the most important processes, the handbook helps streamline workflows and ensures consistency throughout the project's lifecycle. Overall, it acts as a vital resource for maintaining clarity, alignment, and high standards within the team.

The handbook is relevant for

- NEFI operative team
- NEFI+ team including Hub co-leads, works package leaders and team members
- Project leaders and teams of NEFI projects of the Energy Model Region calls
- Project leaders and teams of projects of the RTI Initiative for Transforming Industry

The documents listed in Table 3 are considered relevant and applicable. They form an essential part of the project framework and should be referenced throughout the project lifecycle. In particular, the NEFI website as well as relevant strategy documents will be continuously updated.

Table 3: Relevant documents and information

Document	Link	Access	Relevance
Leitfaden FTI-Initiative für die Transformation der Industrie, Ausschreibung 2024	Leitfaden RTI Initiative	Public	Project leader and members of projects funded by the RTI Initiative Transforming Industry
Leitfaden Berichtslegung Vorzeigeregion Energie, Ausschreibung 2021	Leitfaden Vorzeigeregion Energie – Ausschreibung 2021	Public	Project leaders and members of projects funded in Model Region Energy call

NEFI factsheets, publications, presentations, reports, studies, scoping papers, conference contributions	www.nefi.at Zenodo - NEFI (Repository)	Public	All interested persons
NEFI marketing materials, templates	www.nefi.at Zenodo - NEFI (Repository)	Public	NEFI community
Strategy documents (Target group strategy, Marketing and Communication concept, Exploitation strategy)	Internal strategy documents	Restricted (available upon reasonable request)	CSC, operative team
NEFI cluster reports and NEFI+ innovation lab reports	Internal reports	Restricted (available upon reasonable request)	CSC, operative team
FFG - Förderungsvertrag		Restricted	Concluded between FFG and MUL, AIT, BIZ UP, ESV
Konsortialvertrag		Restricted	Concluded between MUL, AIT, BIZ UP and ESV
Kooperationsvereinbarung		Restricted	Concluded between NEFI+ (represented by MUL) and Hub Co-lead or Board member

4. Initial situation and project context

The NEFI innovation network formed in 2017 around a consortium of the AIT – Austrian Institute of Technology, Montanuniversität Leoben, OÖ Energiesparverband and Business Upper Austria brings together wide-ranging expertise in the fields of energy research and project implementation. This network unites over 120 partners, including more than 104 companies, 8 research and 4 institutional partners. NEFI involves companies from all sectors, such as the food, mechanical engineering, plastics, cement and steel industries. The spectrum of companies involved in NEFI ranges from large leading companies to innovative SMEs. Together they collaborate in 24 research and demonstration projects with a triggered investment volume of approx. 95 Mio. €.

NEFI is an Energy Model Region funded by the Austrian Climate and Energy Fund. The governments of the industrially strong federal states of Upper Austria and Styria back the programme and actively support the development.

In addition, the NEFI consortium has successfully applied for an innovation lab NEFI+ in the context of the RTI Initiative for Transforming Industry, to further pursue the long-term vision and goals of NEFI, developed and strengthened by the former innovation lab NEFI_Lab from 2018 to 2024. Also, NEFI+ can rely on the continuing support of the federal states of Upper Austria and Styria.

The RTI Initiative for Transforming Industry represents a pivotal shift for Austrian industry and research, integrating 320 million EUR in research, technology, and innovation funding within a broader 3 billion EUR national framework for reducing greenhouse gas emissions. This initiative aligns with Austria's ambition to achieve climate-neutrality, creating a platform for groundbreaking industrial solutions and strengthening Austria's position as a leader in sustainable innovation.

NEFI stands as a central actor in this landscape, leveraging its well-established innovation processes and stakeholder networks to address systemic challenges and promote scalable, cross-sectoral solutions. Its focus extends beyond technology to incorporate policy recommendations, resilience strategies, and systemic energy solutions, all while fostering a collaborative ecosystem to drive Austria's industrial transformation toward climate neutrality.

The innovation lab NEFI+ encompasses all support activities within a closed innovation circle (shown in Figure 1), such as innovation hub support, project monitoring and project impact assessment, as well as scenario modelling and impact assessment for industrial pathways to climate neutrality. The results are disseminated through the NEFI Technology Talks and scenario reports to support policymaking and to develop new projects. NEFI+ also supports the project development for the RTI initiative relying on an overall drive from industry to push the transformation further.

Figure 1: NEFI Innovation Circle

5. Governance, contact details and responsibilities

5.1. Governance

The **NEFI network steering committee** is the ultimate decision-making body of NEFI and decides on the strategic focus of NEFI. The steering committee consists of AIT (Austrian Institute of Technology), MUL (Montanuniversität Leoben), ESV (OÖ Energiesparverband) and BIZ (Business Upper Austria) and is chaired by AIT. The **NEFI network coordinator** is responsible for the coordination and efficient implementation of the programme as well as risk management and all legal and contractual issues.

The **innovation lab NEFI+** is a project funded by the RTI Initiative for Transforming Industry and provides the operational framework of the network to drive monitoring, impact assessment, innovation management, dissemination and exploitation. It consists of the same consortium as the NEFI network project and is led by the Montanuniversität Leoben (MUL) - Chair of Energy Network Technology. This setup creates a strong connection between the NEFI network and its innovation lab. In the external communication, the innovation network presents itself under the established NEFI brand, which boasts a high level of recognition.

The Network Steering Committee is supported by an **operative team** composed of members from the four consortium partner institutions. This team manages day-to-day operations (see also section 2).

Within NEFI, the main research, development and innovation activities are carried out through the associated **research, innovation and demonstration projects**, funded by energy model region calls or the RTI initiative Transforming Industry. Project development is a key activity of the **NEFI Innovation Hubs**, specialist networks that aim to initiate critical research and innovation projects. NEFI Hubs focus on various technological pathways that have been identified in the NEFI decarbonisation scenarios to hold promise in terms of developing solutions for the industrial energy transition. Each Hub is led by two expert research institutions, so called **Hub Co-Leads**.

Figure 2: NEFI governance

Furthermore, NEFI and its network steering committee are supported by the following boards:

- **Board of Hub Co-Leads:** NEFI Innovation Hubs are thematic networks led by two leading research institutions in the relevant topic area, referred to as Hub Co-Leads. The hubs aim to develop high-quality research and innovation projects across various climate neutrality pathways, leveraging the proven NEFI innovation process. The Board of Hub Co-Leads serves to connect the hubs and acts as a key strategic interface between NEFI and the projects. This ensures alignment of hub activities with NEFI goals and scenarios. Each Hub Co-Lead is represented on the board by a nominated individual.
- **Industry Board (IB):** consists of at least 5 high-ranking representatives of the Austrian industry and aims to facilitate a strategic partnership between NEFI and Austrian industry. All relevant industrial sectors in Austria can be represented in the IB. The establishment of an IB emphasises the importance of the NEFI goals and underlines the industry’s commitment to reach climate neutral industrial energy systems. The Industry Board fulfils the following functions:
 - Voice of the industry: reflecting the industry's perspective on the NEFI innovation process (e.g. making recommendations to address strategic gaps, validating assumptions for scenarios, and providing expert input across the value chain for systemic and technological solutions)
 - Interface between NEFI and Austrian industry: offering recommendations for potential innovation partners and providing active support in the rollout of NEFI technologies.

- Raising visibility: contributing to disseminating results and supporting NEFI in its internationalisation efforts.
- **Scientific Excellence Board:** consists of 7 to 12 international and national experts and ensures the excellence of the accompanying innovation research. It is also intended to contribute to the strategic development of NEFI by bringing in experience from other programmes and incorporating new scientific, technical, economic, and regulatory perspectives. Additionally, members of the Scientific Excellence Board evaluate the scientific submissions for the NEFI conference.

The NEFI network steering committee maintains consistent close communication with all NEFI stakeholders, such as

- Climate and Energy Fund of the Austrian Government (KLIEN), NEFI contact persons Urban Peyker, Claire Cance for general exchange regarding the RTI Initiative and Katja Hoyer regarding communication and public relations. In general, all communication from the funding agencies is channeled through NEFI and not directly with the hubs or boards.
- Ministry of Climate Action and Energy, main NEFI contacts Susanne Meyer and Sabine Mitter
- FFG – Austrian Research Promotion Agency, main NEFI contacts Gertrud Aichberger and Paul Strasser

5.2. Contact Details

Contact person: PS (MUL)

A list of all contacts including operative team, members of all boards and project leads is kept on the NEFI Teams channel and kept up to date by the NEFI operative team ([TeamsFolder - Contact list](#)).

NEFI project leaders and board members must inform NEFI office (office@nefi.at) of relevant changes including changes in contact details.

5.3. NEFI email address (office@nefi.at)

Contact person: OS (AIT)

The office email address is actively managed, with final responsibility resting with AIT as the Network Coordinator. Access is restricted to designated AIT members from the NEFI Marketing and Communications team.

All inquiries sent to the official NEFI email address will be answered directly whenever possible or forwarded to the appropriate personnel based on the content and nature of the request. Examples thereof are given in Table 4.

Table 4: Example for requests sent to the official NEFI address

Nature of request	Forward to
NEFI factsheet	Project lead behind the developed solution Operative team
Project information	Project lead
Press and media inquiries	Marketing and Communication team
Project idea	Hub co-leads (depending on topic)
General information	Marketing and Communication team
Requests for public representation	Operative team CSC Marketing and Communication
All other	Operative team

5.4. Meeting schedule

Contact person: BG (AIT)

Designation	Agenda / content	Participants	Frequency & duration
CSC Meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General update, risk management - Reporting & decisions PR activities, events & meetings - Reporting & decisions Lab activities - Reporting & decisions Innovation Hubs (2x p.a.) - Any other business, dates, deadlines 	CSC +1 operative support person Hub Co-Leads (2x p. year) Workflow/ WP/ Task – Leads (if required)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2 p. year in person with external guests (e.g. Hub-Co-Leads and other board representatives) - 2 online - additionally on demand - Organised by AIT (BG)
Coordination Meetings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - General update, risk management - Prioritisation of tasks & milestones - Workplans - Update on project development 	MUL (TK, KPS, PS) AIT (BG, RA, SN)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 3-4 weeks & on demand - In person or online - Organised by MUL (KPS)
KLIEN Jour Fixe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Update NEFI → KLIEN, KLIEN → NEFI - Upcoming calls and project development - Monitoring and impact assessment: findings, highlights, recommendations as they arise or status update when requested - Marketing 	AIT: BG MUL: TK, KPS KLIEN representatives BMIMI representatives (optional) If required: PR team (MÖ, OS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 4 weeks - In person or online - Organised by KLIEN - BMIMI informed and invited
Extended thematic meetings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Key topic (e.g. Monitoring, Project and Scenario Impact assessment): highlights, results, recommendations 	NEFI: Subject matter experts KLIEN, BMIMI, other relevant ministries: Thematically interested individuals and representatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On demand, prepared in KLIEN Jour Fixe - In person or online - Organised by KLIEN

NEFI operative telco	<p>(1) Standard reporting</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - project development - company visits - highlights related to NEFI - etc. <p>(2) Reporting & Discussion PR</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Update PR - News & Events - NEFI website - Update on information materials e.g. brochures, pictures, videos - Media requests and press activities - Newsletter - Any other business <p>(3) Reporting & Discussion WPs</p>	<p>AIT: BG, RA, SN, OS, MÖ MUL: KPS, PS, CG, LW BIZ: DW, MG, EB ESV: CÖ</p> <p>For (3): Above mentioned + TT, KHL, GR, CS, GT</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Weekly, 1.5 h - Online - Organised by AIT (BG) - 1x per month (3) instead of (2)
PR team meeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Content planning for upcoming 6 months 	<p>AIT: BG, RA, SN, OS, MÖ MUL: KPS, PS, CG, LW BIZ: DW, MG, EB ESV: CÖ</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2x p. year - In person - Organised by AIT (OS)
WP meetings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - As defined by WP leads 	<p>As required</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On demand - Organised by WP leads - Online or in person
Hub meetings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - As defined by Hub Co-Leads 	<p>As required</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On demand

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organised by Hub Co-leads - Online or in person
Board of Hub Co-Leads	- As defined by CSC	Representatives of all hub co-leads CSC + operative support people	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2x per year - 1x in person, 1x online - Additionally on demand (online or in person) - Organised by ESV (CÖ)
Industrial Board Meeting	- As defined by CSC	Industrial Board members CSC + operative support people as required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On demand - Organised by MUL (KPS) - Online or in person
Scientific Excellence Board meeting	- As defined by CSC	Scientific Excellence Board members CSC + operative support people as required	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On demand - Organised by MUL (KPS) - Online

6. NEFI Monitoring, Impact assessment and Scenario Modelling

6.1. Project performance monitoring

Contact person: RA (AIT)

NEFI supports the RTI initiative and all resulting projects in monitoring and impact analysis. The project impact assessment has been developed by NEFI in the context of an overarching initiative across all three model regions energy, coordinated by the accompanying research (B.A.U.M consult). The developed and successfully applied methodology will be rolled out to all projects in the initiative. Coordination with and reporting to the funding body takes place through yearly reports, advisory board meetings, regular status updates and other key deliverables.

Project Monitoring of Scientific Output

NEFI monitors the projects within the RTI Initiative for Transforming Industry regarding their scientific output, as well as their activities in public outreach and dissemination of results. This includes not only publications in scientific journals but also presentations at conferences, workshops, trade fairs, and similar events. Additionally, the number of theses produced within the framework of the projects is recorded.

Data & Indicators:

- Scientific publications (peer-reviewed journal papers)
- Conference contributions (peer-reviewed conference papers, presentations)
- Bachelor's, Master's, PhD theses
- Patents
- Dissemination activities

Frequency & Type of Data Collection:

- Public data is collected via an open repository (www.zenodo.org) and made publicly available on the website www.nefi.at.
- Data can be continuously entered into the repository, but at least once a year, with a deadline of May 31.
- Sensitive data (e.g., restricted theses) is not published in the repository but used in the form of metadata for monitoring purposes.

Project Impact Assessment

A project impact assessment is crucial for evaluating the effects of climate-neutral solutions and (demonstrator) projects, as the real influence of the developed solutions mainly emerges during roll-out. The specific solutions developed in individual projects are assessed along three dimensions (climate, macro-economic and resilience). Using key assumptions for emission factors, market size and growth and diffusion of the technology the potential impact of the solution can be estimated, and policy recommendations can be developed. The project impact

assessment is strongly intertwined with the NEFI scenario development explained in the chapter below.

NEFI has established and successfully tested a method for techno-economic impact assessment on project-level. The solutions developed within the RTI initiative “Transformation of Industry” are analysed along three dimensions (1)-(3) as well as qualitatively, and the impact of the solutions is extrapolated across all relevant sectors until 2040.

Data & Indicators:

(1) Climate Impact:

- Effects of all measures on CO₂ emissions
- Effects of all measures on primary energy demand

(2) Macroeconomic Impact:

- Effects on investments within Austria (national CAPEX and OPEX)
- Export potential of Austrian products or technologies developed in the project

(3) Resilience:

- Reduction of fossil imports

(4) Qualitative insights and results that are not quantifiable, including recommendations on framework conditions.

Scaling and diffusion of the solution:

- Identification of sectors where a specific solution is relevant
- Potential estimation: maximum effect of the solution under the assumption of 100% rollout
- Roll-out: estimation of realistic diffusion factors (benchmark years 2025 / 2030 / 2035 / 2040)
- Identification of competing technologies / cross-over projects

Frequency & Type of Data Collection:

- Data collection occurs as soon as a specific solution has been developed in the project or, at the latest, upon project completion.
- Data relevant for the impact assessment is collected through interviews with project leaders and via online tools.

6.2. Scenario modelling & performance monitoring

Contact person: LW (MUL)

NEFI has developed three industry demand scenarios conducted for the timeframe 2017 to 2050 as a visionary guideline for stakeholders in manufacturing industry, for policy makers, and for technology providers.

Business as usual (BAU): serving as a reference, the BAU scenario allows to evaluate the effectiveness of innovative technologies in the two transition scenarios below. It is obtained by extrapolating historic trends and taking into account economic development forecasts.

Pathway of industry (POI): the POI scenario is the result of a close dialogue with representatives from leading industrial stakeholders who have assessed the technology deployments in their respective sectors under current and foreseeable boundary conditions until to 2030. The development until 2050 is extrapolated on the basis of this assessment, while taking into account expected technology availability. This scenario is a unique representation of current industrial transformation plans and is well equipped to identify important areas of policy action in efforts to achieve climate neutrality.

Zero emission (ZEM): the ZEM scenario represents the implementation of extensive and ambitious measures that could make Austria's industrial energy system completely climate neutral by 2050. It applies breakthrough technologies which have been identified as the most promising solutions to the transformation challenge on a sector-by-sector basis. A back-casting approach is used to calculate the pathway towards climate neutrality. This means that, starting from the target state of climate neutrality in the year 2050, a reverse pathway is developed indicating the steps leading to the successful achievement of this goal.

By comparison of the scenario results, the bandwidth of different pathways towards industrial climate neutrality can be seen and the most important fields of action can be identified.

Within NEFI+ this scenario modelling is extended and further refined, including a more granular resolution on industry sector level, an exergo-economic optimisation approach and a detailed analysis on industrial value chain restructuring and resilience.

Scenario Impact Assessment

The scenario impact assessment is crucial for evaluating the effects of climate-neutral solutions and international as well as national trends and drivers on the Austrian industry and the energy system. It calculates and analyses pathways for a successful industrial transformation towards climate neutrality including infrastructure requirements and macro-economic considerations, such as total costs per technology strategy. The scenarios take into account data along the three dimensions (climate, macro-economic and resilience) as well as the results of the project impact assessment. Using trends, drivers and key assumptions (for instance regarding emission factors, market size and growth and diffusion of the technology), scenario variants are created and assessed. This sensitivity analysis allows the derivation of policy recommendations, ranging from climate and energy policies to industrial and infrastructure policies, and RTI (research, technology, and innovation) policies.

Data & Indicators:

(1) Climate Impact:

- Effects on CO2 emissions
- Effects on primary energy demand

(2) Macroeconomic Impact:

- Effects on investments within Austria (national CAPEX and OPEX)
- Effects on import, export and foreign trade balance
- Restructuring of industrial value chains

(3) Resilience:

- Reduction of fossil imports
- Development of new dependencies (renewable imports, raw materials, etc.)
- Impact on value chains
- Impact from value chains
- Economical and ecological crisis
- Employment and location security

(4) Qualitative insights and results that are not quantifiable, including recommendations on framework conditions.

Further information on the project and scenario impact assessment can be found on the NEFI website and is continuously updated ([NEFI - Impact](#) and [NEFI - Dekarbonisierungsszenarien](#)). NEFI will regularly offer workshops on related topics, which project leaders are encouraged to attend to deepen their knowledge and facilitate exchange with other experts.

The results from monitoring and impact assessments are aggregated by NEFI and submitted to the funding body in the yearly report. They are also presented to the project leaders and the public, including at the NEFI Conference, NEFI Technology Talks, and the Virtual Industry Lab. Project-specific impact assessment results are made available to the project leader for further dissemination.

A key output of the scenario impact assessment are the regularly updated NEFI scenario results, from which clear recommendations for action towards climate neutrality in industry are derived and discussed with policymakers across different levels, from climate to industrial policy.

7. Reporting

Contact person: RA (AIT)

Formally, the reporting of all activities from NEFI, NEFI+, and the individual projects takes place through the annual written reports and the mandatory jury hearings:

- NEFI: Yearly report including monitoring and impact assessment of the projects with hearing
- NEFI+: yearly reports to FFG via e-call as well as to the federal states of Styria and Upper Austria.
- Projects: yearly reports to FFG via e-call

Additionally, the following reporting activities are conducted as needed:

- Internal NEFI+ reporting: Regular reporting on work packages and Hub activities as part of regular internal communication, as specified in section 5.4 (Meeting schedule). Work package leaders must prepare all information for the adoption of relevant decisions. If a time sensitive decision is required by CSC, work package leaders must contact CSC proactively providing all relevant information. Decisions can then be taken by circular resolution, in telephone conference with minutes or the like.
- Reporting of highlights, findings, derived recommendations to KLIEN and/or BMIMI: As part of regular communication (see section 5.4), findings are reported as they arise, status updates are provided as needed, in particular upon request from the funding authorities. Together, further steps are decided (e.g., presentation in a larger forum with relevant stakeholders, communication plan). This is particularly relevant in the context of monitoring and project/scenario impact assessment, where results are not expected at short intervals, making on-demand communication a more suitable approach (note: this is in addition to the status updates provided in the yearly written reports).

8. Information management & communication

Contact person: MÖ (AIT), OS (AIT)

The experienced NEFI PR team supports projects and hubs in all aspects of external communication, provides marketing materials, and assists with the organisation and promotion of meetings and technology talks. NEFI provides hub descriptions, project descriptions, project results, and other relevant information on the website www.nefi.at.

Furthermore, NEFI promotes the visibility of projects and the dissemination of project results through targeted activities across various channels: in addition to the website, social media channels (e.g., LinkedIn or YouTube) are actively used, NEFI Technology Talks are organised, and various print materials (e.g., NEFI Factsheets) are produced. Funded projects are explicitly encouraged to participate in NEFI events (NEFI Technology Talks, NEFI Conference), engage in the innovation process, and make their results visible through presentations (e.g., at the NEFI Conference) and publications (e.g., NEFI Factsheets).

NEFI has conducted a comprehensive stakeholder analysis and based on the results, developed a target group and communication strategy, including the channels used. This strategy is reviewed at least annually for relevance and adapted as needed ([Teams - Strategic documents](#)).

8.1. Marketing material

Contact person: OS (AIT)

NEFI provides marketing material (such as roll ups, flyers, factsheets, infosheets, presentations, templates and logos) free for download on the NEFI website via Zenodo ([Downloadbereich - NEFI](#)).

NEFI Factsheets

A key format in NEFI's solution-centered communication are NEFI factsheets ([Downloadbereich - NEFI](#)). Each factsheet covers a solution developed in NEFI and addresses customers and users explaining the advantages of the solution and first steps for an implementation.

8.2. Newsletter

Contact person: OS (AIT)

An official NEFI newsletter is sent four times a year to keep all people interested in NEFI informed about project highlights, NEFI activities and events. Contributions to the newsletter can be coordinated with NEFI marketing and communications.

In addition, the NEFI communications team contributes articles to the KLIEN newsletter which appears four times a year ([KLIEN Newsletter](#)).

People can register for the NEFI newsletter via <https://www.nefi.at/newsletter/>. A withdrawal from the mailing list is possible by clicking the unsubscribe link at the bottom of the newsletter. The official NEFI newsletter mailing list is stored on the newsletter server (Mailjet – see also Section 12 Access and data management).

All official NEFI mailing towards the NEFI mailing list or part thereof occurs from office@nefi.at and must include an unsubscribe option (in accordance with the requirements of the General Data Protection Regulation).

8.3. Website

Contact person: OS (AIT)

The website www.nefi.at offers public information about NEFI such as

- Goals, vision, mission
- Impact
- Internationalisation efforts
- Innovation hubs, projects, services and solutions developed
- Publications such as papers, factsheets, studies (e.g. decarbonisation scenarios) via link to www.zenodo.org ([Zenodo - NEFI](#))
- Contacts
- News and events

8.4. Social media

Contact person: OS (AIT)

NEFI uses social media channels for communication both within and outside the NEFI community. They should be used actively by all NEFI partners to ensure maximum reach of the social media campaigns. NEFI project leaders and partners can use NEFI social media channels to generate attention to NEFI-relevant topics in coordination with the NEFI communications team.

- X ([X - NEFI](#))
- LinkedIn ([LinkedIn - NEFI](#))
- YouTube ([YouTube - NEFI](#))

The social media accounts can be accessed and are regularly monitored by marketing and communications. Final responsibility for the accounts rests with AIT as WP2 leader.

8.5. Project logo and acknowledgements

Contact person: OS (AIT)

All communication material (e.g. posters, flyers, presentations) must include the official NEFI project logo which can be downloaded from the NEFI website as well as a reference to the NEFI website and a NEFI contact such as:

„Weitere Informationen zu NEFI – New Energy for Industry sowie zu den NEFI-Projekten finden Sie auf der NEFI-Website unter www.nefi.at oder erhalten Sie direkt über das NEFI-Büro: office@nefi.at.“

or

“For more information about the NEFI – New Energy for Industry and the NEFI projects, please visit the NEFI website at www.nefi.at or contact the NEFI office directly at office@nefi.at.”

In addition, projects have to include acknowledgements and logos from the funding agencies as specified by the guidelines of the funding call.

- In the case of Energy Model Region calls this includes the “Klimafonds” and the “Vorzeigeregion Energie” logos as well as
“Dieses Projekt wird aus Mitteln des Klima- und Energiefonds gefördert und im Rahmen der FTI-Initiative „Vorzeigeregion Energie“ durchgeführt.“

or

„This project is supported with the funds from the Climate and Energy Fund and implemented in the framework of the RTI-initiative “Flagship region Energy”.“

- In the case of the calls of the RTI-initiative for Transforming Industry this includes the “Klimafonds” logo as well as
“Dieses Projekt wird aus Mitteln des Klima- und Energiefonds gefördert und im Rahmen der FTI-Initiative für die Transformation der Industrie durchgeführt.“

or

„This project is supported with the funds from the Climate and Energy Fund and implemented in the framework of the RTI-initiative for Transforming Industry.”.

For further details, refer to the corresponding guidelines.

Furthermore, for general NEFI and NEFI+ activities, the official logos of the co-financing Federal States of Styria and Upper Austria have to be used.

8.6. Presentation template

Contact person: RA (AIT)

An up-to-date version of the presentation template as well as short presentations about NEFI (1 slide, 3 or 20 slides) and NEFI projects can be downloaded from Zenodo through the NEFI website. NEFI partners must use the template for presentations related to NEFI projects.

8.7. Events

Contact person: OS (AIT)

All upcoming and past NEFI events are listed on the NEFI website (www.nefi.at/events/). Also, registration to events can be done through the NEFI website (Eventbrite).

NEFI Technology Talks

The NEFI Technology Talks are a series of events addressing current technical and systemic issues related to the industrial energy transition. The NEFI Technology Talks are held 1–2 per month, either in person or online. These events focus on technological or systemic solutions, taking into account aspects such as policy and legislation. When Technology Talks are organised by the NEFI Innovation Hubs, they include an interactive workshop component aimed at project development. By engaging stakeholders from industry, academia, and policy-making, the NEFI Technology Talks create a dynamic platform for advancing sustainable energy solutions.

NEFI Conference

The NEFI Conference is an international scientific conference and takes place every 2 years. The transformation of the industrial energy system to a climate-neutral energy supply is an essential contribution to achieving the national climate targets and can only succeed with innovations and the development of concrete solutions. The NEFI-New Energy for Industry innovation network invites national and international experts to present the latest scientific findings and discuss the energy transition in Austrian industry with high-ranking representatives from industry, research and politics. The scientific contributions center on the topics of the NEFI Innovation Hubs. The next NEFI conference is planned for 2026.

9. Workflows and standard procedures

9.1. Workflow for new projects

Contact person: BG (AIT), KPS (MUL)

Purpose: Define the steps required to develop and onboard new projects effectively

Steps:

1. Initiation:
 - Submission of project idea/proposal to NEFI Team and/or associated NEFI innovation hub
2. NEFI+ support in the proposal phase:
 - Initial evaluation by NEFI Hub Co-Leads and identification of potential support need
 - Align the project goals with NEFI objectives and funding guidelines.
 - Identify potential risks and resource needs.
3. Onboarding:
 - Assign project lead and operational support.
 - Share project templates and relevant guidelines (e.g., NEFI Handbook, NEFI Innovation Hubs Textbausteine, for project proposal, reporting requirements).
4. Submission:
 - Submit the approved project proposal to the funding agency for evaluation and approval.
5. NEFI+ support during the project runtime:
 - In particular with exploitation, public relation, and monitoring

9.2. Workflow for LinkedIn posts

Contact person: OS (AIT)

Purpose: Active project communication while ensuring consistency and quality in NEFI's social media communications.

Steps:

1. Content Drafting:
 - Submit a draft post to the marketing and communication team (AIT: MÖ, OS) via email: office@nefi.at.
 - Include visuals, hashtags, and desired publication timing.
2. Review & Approval:
 - Marketing team reviews content for alignment with NEFI's messaging and branding.
 - Approval by the NEFI communications lead (MÖ or OS).
3. Scheduling:
 - Schedule post for optimal reach using LinkedIn's analytics.

4. Monitoring:
 - Track engagement and report insights during the next PR team meeting.

9.3. Workflow for NEFI Technology Talk

Contact person: OS (AIT)

Purpose: Efficient organisation of NEFI Technology Talks applying a well-established and standardised process for organisation and marketing. The NEFI team organises Technology Talks for associated projects and NEFI Innovation Hubs free of charge.

Steps:

1. Registration:
 - Express interest via office@nefi.at, providing event details and participant information.
2. Approval:
 - NEFI operative team evaluates relevance and availability of resources.
 - Approval communicated to the participant.
3. Preparation:
 - Selecting the date, location and time schedule.
 - Set up registration as well as promoting the event (e.g. NEFI website, social media, newsletter).
 - Share presentation templates and guidelines.
 - Ensure alignment of content with NEFI goals.
4. Execution:
 - Participate in the event and distribute approved NEFI materials.
5. Follow-Up:
 - Provide feedback and report highlights to the NEFI team via email, or in person.
 - NEFI publishes recap of the event on the website and other channels

9.4. Workflow for NEFI Solution

Contact person: RA (AIT)

Purpose: Communication of solutions developed in NEFI projects by generating a solution website as well as a NEFI factsheet

Steps:

1. Expression of interest
 - Express interest via office@nefi.at or during exploitation interview
 - Submit a draft factsheet and further information about the solution to be published of the NEFI website
2. Approval
 - NEFI operative team evaluates relevance and alignment with NEFI goals

- Draft factsheet is reviewed and formatted according to guidelines for factsheets
- 3. Publishing
 - The solution is published together with the factsheet on the NEFI website
 - The factsheet is uploaded to the data repository Zenodo

9.5. Workflow for the reporting of dissemination activities (e.g. publications)

Contact person: RA (AIT)

Purpose: Capture and deposit publications and other dissemination activities

Steps:

1. Information of NEFI regarding dissemination activities
 - Fill out the Dissemination report ([Download Area - NEFI](#))
 - Send the report to office@nefi.at
 - Send the original document (publication, report, study, presentation etc.) to office@nefi.at if it is approved for upload to the data repository
2. Upload
 - NEFI operative team uploads the publication to the data repository Zenodo
 - NEFI operative team links the file in the download section
3. Marketing
 - If desired, the NEFI marketing team supports the dissemination of the activity (e.g. newsletter, social media etc.)

10. Quality assurance within NEFI+ project execution

Contact person: PS (MUL)

The Quality Assurance (QA) sets standards for ensuring high-quality outcomes, transparency, and compliance with all funding and operational regulations. The plan emphasises systematic, continuous improvement processes and proactive risk management across all phases of NEFI+ project execution.

Part of the project management is the monitoring of the overall progress of the NEFI+ project mainly based on the information which is collected by the Work Package leaders and Task leaders according to the milestone plan.

10.1. NEFI disclosure approval process

All information and documentation that are made accessible to 3rd parties (i.e. organisations and persons outside of the NEFI+ consortium) has to undergo an approval mechanism (see NEFI+ consortial agreement §3.3.5). This ensures that as much information as possible is distributed consistently without breaking confidentiality.

10.2. Progress deviations and corrective actions

The project management ensures the quality and timeliness of milestones, project reports and deliverables.

Open issues occur during project execution. They are kept track of and discussed as needed in the weekly operative meetings. Their status as well as conclusion is recorded in the minutes of the meeting ([TeamsFolder - Minutes](#)).

Deviations from the work plan must be documented, reported and addressed. Corrective actions are taken in a bottom-up approach and are primarily adopted within the respective work package. The Work Package Leader will supply an updated work plan for the work package that will substitute the original plan. Problems affecting more than one work package or even the overall success of the project are reported in the operative meeting and dealt with at CSC level. The CSC together with all affected work package leaders will elaborate an updated work plan.

If a partner fails to fulfill their obligations, the CSC may reassign the respective task(s) to another partner to avoid unnecessary delays in the overall project. The decision will be made following appropriate consultation within the CSC.

10.3. Financial management

Financial management comprehends all areas of financial planning, budgeting, auditing, submission of financial statements/invoices, receipt and distribution of funds from the funding bodies, as well as the handling of expenditures for any centrally managed items on behalf of the entire consortium. Effective financial monitoring, carried out by each partner, is a crucial

activity. This is reported in the annual interim report and submitted to the FFG as part of the financial management process. When financial monitoring is properly organised, project related risks can be significantly reduced.

10.4. Ethics & Gender Issues

The general ethics and gender equality framework applied in NEFI+ will guarantee and safeguard fundamental rights such as gender equality, privacy, data protection, sustainability and security. This especially means that all NEFI partners are fully committed to privacy, security, sustainability and gender equality policies.

11. Risk management

Contact person: PS (MUL)

The major aim of risk management is to identify potential risks as early as possible and either to eliminate or (at least) to reduce the damage that might be caused through those risks. Failure to adequately manage risks might threaten the whole success of the NEFI project.

11.1. Risk assessment and mitigation measures

Risk assessment and management will be conducted throughout the whole project lifetime to ensure that all risks are carefully monitored. It is usually impossible to eliminate all risks, but they can be recognised and dealt with. The risk management process requires that each risk is assessed and appropriate measures need to be taken to prevent the particular risk or to minimise the corresponding effect.

NEFI structures its risks in three levels:

- (A) High level: comprises external factors influencing the NEFI cluster and the impact of NEFI on external settings
- (B) Medium level: refers to the NEFI cluster itself
- (C) Low level: refers to the sub-project level.

While risk management for level A and B will primarily be placed under the responsibility of the cluster coordinator, level C risks are the responsibility of the project leaders.

At the beginning of the NEFI project, a list of risks was identified. It shall be reviewed and updated as required or at least once a year in the context of the yearly reporting.

CSC members use their in-house risk management guidelines and procedures to identify risks at an early stage. Newly identified risks (including project risks influencing the performance of NEFI) must be reported proactively to the CSC (in meetings, telcos or via email). The following information shall be provided ([a risk reporting template can be found on the NEFI website](#)):

- Type of risk: Technical, legal/regulatory, economic, operational, social, other
- Risk level: A, B or C
- Probability: low, medium, high
- Detailed description of risk
- Impact and quantification (in €, if possible)
- Proposed risk mitigation measures

The CSC decides on the risk mitigation strategy.

If necessary, the cluster coordinator - or, for C-level (project) risks, the project leader - will inform the funding bodies (KLIEN and KPC) and manage all related communication.

Table 5: Risk analysis and risk mitigation

Nr	Risk	Risk Category	WP	Detailed description of risk	Risk level	Probability of occurrence	Proposed risk mitigation measures
1	A partner leaves the consortium	Organisational, economic, operational	All	A partner must file for bankruptcy, or a partner wants to leave the consortium	B	Low	Transparent, regular communication. In case a partner leaves the consortium a transfer the project tasks to another project partner will be put in place. These decisions are to be taken by the Cluster Steering Committee.
2	Ensuring confidentiality of data/results	Organisational, technical	All	Difficulties in the exploitation and dissemination of project results	C	Low	Early establishment of data management plan, within the framework of agreements and contracts (consortium agreement) will define standards for data confidentiality and will ensure an open innovation process wherever possible.
3	Co-funding of regional government of Styria or Upper Austria is shortened/cancelled	Economic, organisational	All	In the event of an unexpected financial policy change or budget reallocation by the regional governments of Styria or Upper Austria, there is a risk that co-funding support for the NEFI+ initiative may be reduced or cancelled.	A	Low	The regional governments of Styria and Upper Austria have shown support for the NEFI+ (see attached LOS). In the unlikely case of a reduction or cancelation of their grant, NEFI+ will either re-dimensioned in accordance with the Cluster Steering Committee and the funding agencies or be financed through own capital resources of the partners and services. Moreover, since NEFI+ is a nation-wide programme, other

Nr	Risk	Risk Category	WP	Detailed description of risk	Risk level	Probability of occurrence	Proposed risk mitigation measures
							regions could take the open funding gap. In this case the NEFI+ coordinator would seek for additional funding from other regions with sub-projects in this cluster to limit the risk of budget cuts occurring. However, the likelihood of co-funding cuts during the project is low since the regional governments are very reliable partners.
4	The budget of the programme “RTI Transforming Industry” is cut due to political and/or financial crises	Economic, organisational	All	The "RTI Transforming Industry" programme has political and financial support. However, in the rare event of a financial or political crisis, there is a minimal risk of budget impact, which could affect the NEFI+ initiative's scope and timelines.	A	Low	The NEFI+ programme will be re-dimensioned in accordance with the Cluster Steering Committee and the funding agencies.

Nr	Risk	Risk Category	WP	Detailed description of risk	Risk level	Probability of occurrence	Proposed risk mitigation measures
5	Too few projects being developed. The results from Transformation support does not lead to appropriate project proposals	Organisational	2,3,4	There is a risk that support for the reorganisation will not generate enough suitable project proposals, which could limit the effectiveness and impact of NEFI+.	B	Medium	Monitoring of progress is an essential aspect of the NEFI+ and will be performed on three different levels and will allow early risk identification. Within the NEFI+ clear responsibilities and a realisation schedule will limit the risk. Moreover, the NEFI+ is in close contact with funding authorities to work out mitigation- and countermeasures if e.g. to high hurdles for industry to contribute to projects are identified or if findings from transformations support do not find clearly enough their way to funding programme descriptions.
6	Delays in project execution or project goals not achieved	Organisational, operational	All	Delays in work packages or work performance due to staff turnover or unforeseen events	B	Medium	Regular progress reviews and systematic monitoring of respective milestones, with a particular focus on critical ones, complemented by flexible project scheduling to adapt to delays. Increased collaboration and strengthened internal communication supported by backup resources, targeted resource allocation, and external support, as needed. All of this is combined with enhanced documentation and transparency.

Nr	Risk	Risk Category	WP	Detailed description of risk	Risk level	Probability of occurrence	Proposed risk mitigation measures
7	Low engagement of stakeholders and actors in the open innovation process	Social, organisational, operational	3, 4	Planned activities lead to no meaningful results and conclusions due to lack of response/interest	C	Low	Proactive stakeholder engagement strategy, including regular updates and inclusive communication channels. Tailored communication and involvement strategies based on stakeholder interests. Incentives and awareness programmes to encourage active participation. Open dissemination and exploitation strategy to raise awareness, guaranty a high visibility and increase the attractiveness for relevant stakeholders. The risk is considered as low since our experience from NEFI and NEFI_lab shows us large interest from our stakeholder groups.
8	Conflicts of interest between stakeholders and actors	Social, organisational, economic	4	Planned activities or involvement of stakeholders and actors are hindered by conflicting interests	C	Medium	Facilitate regular dialogue and conflict resolution meetings among stakeholders. Clear delineation of roles and transparent decision-making processes.

Nr	Risk	Risk Category	WP	Detailed description of risk	Risk level	Probability of occurrence	Proposed risk mitigation measures
9	Legal conditions hinder cooperative logics and innovative business models	Social, regulatory	3, 6	Difficulties in implementing and utilising results	C	Low	Engage legal experts to navigate regulatory requirements and seek necessary exemptions. Propose adjustments to business models to comply with legal frameworks. Collaboration with regulators to seek flexibility where possible
10	Insufficient cooperation	Social, organisational, operational	All	Reaching of Milestones is not possible due to lack of or insufficient cooperation	B	Low	Foster a culture of open and clear communication for enabling smooth collaboration to achieve milestones.
11	Poor data foundation/poor data quality	Technical, organisational, operational	3	Due to poor data foundation or data quality and data availability, no meaningful results can be achieved; difficulties in Impact Assessment; monitoring and/or validation phase too short	C	Medium	Use data validation rules to identify and correct anomalies early in the data pipeline.
12	Results are not meaningfully scalable	Technical, organisational	3	Due to the different conditions and complexities of the regions, no meaningful results for transferability and scalability can be achieved	C	High	Develop adaptable solutions to account for regional differences. Incorporate feedback loops for ongoing adjustments to improve scalability.

12. Access and data management

Contact person: KPS (MUL), LW (MUL)

The following table provides an overview of the gathered data, how it is organised, stored and to whom it is available. Exclusively data that is necessary for the project performance will be collected, and as far as possible, participants will not be asked to provide personal data. The NEFI operative team will ensure that any personal data which might be collected and handled during the project will be managed properly (according to the European GDPR regulations and according to the Austrian DSGVO).

Table 6: Information on data collected during the project, storage locations, and access permissions

Storage location	Access permission	Data
Data storage		
NEFI+ operatives Team MS Teams Channel	CSC and operative team	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All working documents relevant to the NEFI consortium (e.g. working plan) • Templates • Finalised reports, meeting minutes, marketing materials and presentations • NEFI contact list
NEFI+ Hub Co Leads MS Teams Channel	CSC and operative team Representatives of Hub Co-Leads	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hub Scoping Papers • Supporting documents for project development
Local data storage of project partners		
Communication, dissemination and exploitation tools		
Virtual Industry Lab	AIT	
office@nefi.at	AIT: OS	Incoming emails incl. event registration (distributed if relevant according to Table 4)
NEFI website www.nefi.at	Open access (read) AIT (write)	General information
Eventbrite for events (e.g. registration)	AIT: OS	Participants' information. Eventbrite stores the data in data centers in the USA. An

		account must be created to register for an event and Eventbrite's terms and conditions apply.
Mailjet for newsletter	AIT: OS	Contact data is stored in Mailjet data centers with Google Cloud Platform in Frankfurt (Germany) and Saint-Ghislain (Belgium).
Zenodo (data repository) Zenodo - NEFI	Open access (read) Restricted access for internal files: NEFI@Zenodo community members	Zenodo is an open dissemination research data repository hosted by CERN (Switzerland) and funded primarily by the European Commission, CERN and NIH. <u>Data</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publications • Reports • Marketing material (e.g. factsheets) • Presentations